

Navigating the Path of STEM Education with English Instruction

- Challenges and Benefits -

Soobong SHIN

Vice Rector of IUT

Vice Rector for Research and External Affairs of IUT

(former Vice President for Academic Affairs of INHA Univ.)

Education: all in Civil Engineering

(BS) Seoul National University

(MS) MIT

(Ph.D) University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Career related to Engineering Education

2012~2016 Director of INHA Intellectual Property Education Center

2014~2015 Vice Director of INHA WISET (Women in Science, Eng., and Technology)

2015~2018 Director of INHA Innovative Engineering Education Center

2018~2020 Director of Research Center for Innovative Engineering Education

2020~2022 Director of Research & Information Center for Innovative Engineering Education

(<https://ricee.or.kr/www>)

2016.11.08 Lee Ki-Jun Engineering Innovation Award (KSEE)

Major Social Activities

2009~current Committee Manager of ISO/TC 71/SC 7

2015~current Member of NAEK (National Academy of Engineering of Korea)

2017~2019 President of EESK (Earthquake Engineering Society of Korea)

Language – for what?

English

Communication

STEM – for what?

STEAM **Future Talents**

Role of Language and Culture in STEM Learning

English Learners in STEM Subjects: Transforming Classrooms, Schools, and Lives (National Academics Press, 2018)

- **Language** is simultaneously a cognitive ability and a cultural resource that children first learn to draw on in their homes and communities.
- All of the experiences in families, communities, and cultural contexts, can provide resources for learning **STEM**.
- To learn STEM subjects, students will learn the requisite **new patterns of language and expression** only through opportunity for and engagement in STEM disciplinary practices.
- When allowed to interact in varied ways to build from what they already know and to develop new technical knowledge at school, students can learn STEM content and practices while simultaneously building their proficiency in English beyond STEM.

Why STEM Education?

The solution is STEM education. (EuroSchool)

- STEM courses help our future generation to overcome problems.
- It trains students to solve **the greatest challenges the world may face**.
- It is not just a subject at school.
- **Critical thinking, Problem-solving, Teamwork, Communication, Creativity**, etc.

STEM education in USA.

- Many technical education fields are adopting the idea of STEM education.
- the view is that **students' experiences with real-life problems** will increase their relevance to the STEM field and stimulate change in the workforce and interest in the STEM field (Brown et al., 2011).
- STEM knowledge is **required to solve everyday work-related problems** (Asunda, 2012).

Sustainable Development Goals

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

17 GOALS TO TRANSFORM OUR WORLD

1 NO POVERTY 	2 ZERO HUNGER 	3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING 	4 QUALITY EDUCATION 	5 GENDER EQUALITY 	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION
7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY 	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH 	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE 	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES 	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES 	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION
13 CLIMATE ACTION 	14 LIFE BELOW WATER 	15 LIFE ON LAND 	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS 	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS 	

Grand Challenges for Engineering

<https://www.engineeringchallenges.org/challenges.aspx>

Advanced Personalized Learning

Make Solar Energy Economical

Enhance Virtual Reality

Reverse-Engineering the Brain

Engineer Better Medicines

Advance Health Informatics

Restore and Improve Urban Infrastructure

Secure Cyberspace

Provide Access to Clean Water

Provide Energy from Fusion

Prevent Nuclear Terror

Manage the Nitrogen Cycle

Develop Carbon Sequestration Methods

Engineer the Tools of Scientific Discovery

Problem Definition

Solution Scheme - TRIZ

TRIZ : Teoriya Reshnya Izobretalskikh Zadatch (Russian)

TIPS : Theory of Inventive Problem Solving (English)

- Genrich Altshuller (1926~1998)
- Analyzed more than 200,000 IPs in 1940's
- More than 98% of invents by known sol.
- Only 2% of invents are pioneering.

- ✓ Creativity can be learned.
- ✓ The process of creativity can be discovered and accessed by people who want to solve creative problems.
- ✓ An algorithm for invention exists.

Solution Scheme - TRIZ

제 1차 트리즈 전문가 심화 교육 과정 (트리즈 3레벨 전문가 양성)

● 일시: 2011년 2월4일~19일 ● 장소: 한국산업기술대 TIP 509호 ● 주최: 트리즈 혁신 연구소

Solution Scheme – Design Thinking

“Design thinking is a human-centered approach to innovation that draws from the designer’s toolkit to integrate the needs of people, the possibilities of technology, and the requirements for business success.”

-Tim Brown,
Chair of IDEO

The main tenet of design thinking is empathy for the people you’re trying to design for. Leadership is exactly the same thing - building empathy for the people that you’re entrusted to help.

— David M. Kelley —

AZ QUOTES

Solution Scheme – Design Thinking

Stanford University – d.school

HASSO PLATTNER
Institute of Design at Stanford

Creativity

1800 - 2019 ▾ English (2019) ▾ Case-Insensitive Smoothing ▾

- The word 'creativity' began to be used rapidly in the early 20th century.
- It was only about 100 years ago that humans became 'creative' like God.

Search in Google Books

Rapidly Changing Society

Frequently reported News:

- Employees are laid off by international co. due to the introduction of **AI** in jobs.
- Technological advancements are happening on a daily basis.

- ✓ Jobs are getting automated rapidly.
- ✓ What would happen in the future?

AI in STEM Education

<https://stemeducationjournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40594-022-00377-5>

Existing literature review of AIEd articles, ranging from 2011 to 2021

ChatGPT in 2022

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ChatGPT>

ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pretrained Transformer)

- LLM-based chatbot developed by OpenAI and launched on Nov. 30, 2022.
- It enables users to refine and steer a conversation towards a desired length, format, style, level of detail, and language.
- Successive prompts and replies, known as prompt engineering, are considered at each conversation stage as a context.
- By January 2023, it had become what was then the fastest-growing consumer software application in history, gaining over 100 million users.
- It is a real turning point of AI application: **Singularity**

Revolution – Knowledge & Technology

MOUSE:

- GUI (Graphical User Interface)
- GPU (Graphics Processing Unit)

TOUCH:

- Apple *i*-phone, *i*-pad

VOICE:

- GPT-4
- Google Assistant
- Samsung Gauss
- etc.

AI in STEM Education

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5 Ways AI is Impacting STEM Education:

1. Personalized Assistance
2. Greater creativity
3. Inclusion and Access
4. More accurate Assessments
5. Preparation for the Future

AI's Role in STEM Education:

- AI and other cutting-edge technologies play a huge role in the future of education, especially for STEM students who will develop future programs.
- Embracing AI early on in their learning careers is essential to ensure academic and career success.

Artificial Intelligence
in STEM Education

AI & Language Learning

Hyper-scale AI: (GPT_3.0/4.0)

- **LLM** - Learning to speak and writing is possible. (eg. 3-line poem)
- Accurate transmission of knowledge is possible to some extent.
- But, conveying emotions is difficult.

Learning:

- **Generative AI** can improve productivity and helps with writing.
- Training trillion times to match words:

(eg) I __ home. || I go home and ____.

Hate speech and Hallucination:

- Need rules or engines to exclude hate words.
- Biased information by AI

(eg) nurse → 'she' || doctor, engineer → 'he'

AI & Language Learning

Samsung Gauss AI:

- It will be installed on the Galaxy S24 in January 2024.
- Generative AI – language, image, code models

Samsung Gauss

Machine Learning과 AI 기술의 근본이 되는 정규분포 이론을 정밀한 천재 수학자 칼 프리드리히 가우스, 그의 이름을 따른 삼성 생성형 AI 모델은 세상의 모든 현상과 지식을 담겠다는 의미를 가지고 있으며 텍스트, 코드, 이미지, 영상, 오디오 및 멀티/합성 미디어까지 아우르는 삼성 생성형 AI모델의 세계관을 포함하고 있다.

Apple GPT

AI biased toward English culture.

- AI is becoming a foundational technology thru hyper-scale AI technology.
- However, AI is based on collected DATA (**mostly in English**).
- (eg) Which country does Dokdo(Takeshima) belong to?
 - Google, Chat_GPT → Conflict area
 - Claude 2, Lama 2: → Japan(in Lama 2, Korean language data is also included but less than 0.06%)
- It may be possible to highly depend on English culture rather than being dependent on global big data.

Example of STEM Education

K-12 Education:

- **Science Fair Projects:** Students engage in experiments and present their findings, applying scientific methods.
- **Robotics Clubs:** Schools may have clubs or classes where students build and program robots, integrating technology, engineering, and mathematics.
- **Math Olympiads:** Competitions that challenge students in complex mathematical problem-solving.

GENERATIVE AI in K12 Education:

Opportunities and Challenges for
School District Leaders

Presented by:

Example of STEM Education

Incheon Office of Education – Plan for 2024:

- **Creative Convergence Camp with Uzbekistan:**
 - ✓ Experience booth
 - ✓ Online exchange program with Tashkent students and teachers
 - ✓ Exchange program agreement with sister schools in Tashkent
 - ✓ Inviting UZ Education officials to Korea and Operating a booth at the Incheon Science Festival

Example of STEM Education

Higher Education:

- **Engineering Degrees:** Programs that focus on applied mathematics, physics, and technology, preparing students for careers in engineering fields.
- **Computer Science Courses:** Courses that teach programming, software development, and the theoretical aspects of computing.
- **Research Projects:** In science and engineering courses, students often undertake research projects that apply theoretical knowledge to real-world problems.

Example of STEM Education

EEIC Program in Korea

(Engineering Education Innovation Center)

Cycle 1
'12~'15

Cycle 2
'15~'18

Cycle 3
'18~'22

67 Centers	80 Centers	77 Centers	75 Centers	74 Centers
5 Hub Centers + 60 Centers	6 Hub Centers + 63 Centers	6 Hub Centers + 59 Centers	6 Hub Centers + 58 Centers	12 consortiums + 50 Centers
	1 Tech. Hub Center+ 9 Centers	1 Tech. Hub Center + 9 Centers	1 Tech. Hub Center + 9 Centers	1 Tech. consortium + 10 Centers
	1 Engineering Education Research Center (Yeon-Se Univ.)	1 Engineering Education Research Center (inha Univ.)	Research & Information Center for innovative Engineering Education (inha Univ.)	Research & Information Center for innovative Engineering Education (inha Univ.)
		1 Engineering Education Information Center (Korean Society for Engineering Education)		
2 Science and Engineering Convergence Center (Yonsei Univ., Handong Univ.)				

Example of STEM Education

Phase III EEIC Consortium

The number in a parenthesis is the number of participating university.

Example of STEM Education

Since
2012

공학과 산업 사이

2012년부터 사회적공헌재단의 주선으로 공학계와 산업계 사이

공학은 만들고 산업은 생산한다.

삼척이 만든 계룡산이 시간이 지나며 느꼈으며, 서울주행차로 서울엔터프라이즈 IoT로 산업수업에서 평가되고 있다.

공학의 인재가 산업의 인재로 성장하고 있다. 공학의 도전에 산업의 혁신이다.

본 자료는 공학계와 산업계 간의 교류를 촉진하기 위한 목적으로 제작되었습니다. 무단 전재 및 재배포를 금지합니다.

Example of STEM Education

Vertically Integrated Project

- World-wide VIP consortium
- Form a team with multi-grade and multi-disciplinary students of Engineering College
- Participate in carrying out practical research tasks suggested by the Professor
- For a total of 6 semesters, from the 2nd semester of freshmen year to the 1st semester of senior year

theory-based education

project-based education

Q&A

